

Review on Probiotics as A Health Supplement

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ABSTRACT

The organisational characteristics of microbial cells and their function in a probiotic will be the primary topics of this review. Spatial organisation is a quality that sets all biological systems apart. Even the smallest biological organisms, bacteria, have precise internal structures and well-defined geometries. This review will additionally shed light regarding how these probiotics support our bodies' ability to maintain a healthy balance and avoid numerous diseases. They achieve this by decreasing inflammation and strengthening our immune systems. The most common microbial species for this purpose include *Saccharomyces boulardi*, *Bacillus coagulans*, and *Lactobacillus plantarum*, among other probiotic bacteria classifications that are frequently listed. Many investigations have found that the advantage that microorganisms have in their improved association with human microflora is more advantageous than it is with other animals.

Keywords: Probiotic, GUT Flora, Vitamin, GIT track, Microbs

INTRODUCTION

Probiotics were first proposed in 1908 by "Nobel Prize winner Eli Metchnikoff", who hypothesized that the long lives of Bulgarian peasants were due to their eating foods made from fermented milk. Stillwell and Lilly used the word "probiotic" first in the year of 1965 to highlight the chemicals produced by one microbes that promote the another microbial growth. "Marteau et al." highlighted them as "microbial preparations or components of microbial cells that have a beneficial effect on health and well-being" in 2002. [2][5] Numerous microorganisms that are present in skin, mouth, GI tract & various part of the body. The GI tract, with surface area of more than 400 m², it contains of commensal microbes highest in our body. More than 500 distinct bacterial species are found in the rich flora of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT), some of them have good health benefits like boosting immunity, protecting the person from invasive harmful microbes. The gut microbiota is captured quickly after born, stays mostly constant throughout our lifetime, and it is critical to maintaining homeostasis of human. An individual and distinct intestinal immune system evolves as a result of interactions between developing the host and intestinal microbiota. The task of the mucosal system

immune of host is to separate between infections and benign species by inducing protective immunity and avoiding the inflammatory action which can disbalance the integrity of gut mucosa. [12][5]

1.2. Definition of Probiotics:

Live microorganisms known as probiotics can be added to a wide range of goods, such as medications, food products, and dietary supplements. The term "probiotic" refers to a relatively recent concept—that of microorganisms that have positive effects on both humans and animals. [1][6] An Expert Group described probiotics as "live microorganisms which upon ingestion in certain numbers exert health benefits beyond inherent general nutrition." The name probiotic means "for life." [4]. The FAO/WHO Expert Consultation is of the opinion that broad recommendations regarding the testing and validation of these microorganisms' safety and possible health benefits for human administration are necessary. The two probiotics that are most frequently utilized in food and feed are *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*. Probiotics also include other bacteria such as *Bacillus* species, some *Escherichia coli* strains, and yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. Since ancient times, lactic acid bacteria (LAB), which are used to ferment food,

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have been employed for both purposes. [14] LAB can ferment food and may also have health advantages. According to reports, LABs are GRAS (generally acknowledged as safe) and do not possess any pathogenic or virulence characteristics. Certain desirable properties, like low cost, ability to maintain viability throughout processing and storage, ease of application in goods, and resistance to physical and chemical processing, should be taken into consideration for the use of LAB as probiotics. [18]

2.1. Good & Bad Microbes:

Numerous microorganisms in our body cooperate to carry out various tasks. Which can found in our GIT track are the mostly. They enhance the ingestion and digestion of food. They can fulfil a lot of the corns in our digestion. Alternatively, a variety of pathogenic varieties of various microorganisms will take over and misdigest our food. In the course of breaking down our meal, they will even add certain toxins to it. As a result, our health will really deteriorate with each dietary cycle (Amara, 2012). Many illnesses are ignored and not diagnosed when, in reality, their main primary reason is the presence of harmful bacteria in the digestive tract. This is mostly because of leakage from eating procedures, lifestyle c, or even sickness of themselves, which increase the scales in favour of harmful bad bacteria. [10][3]

2. Microbial Species as Probiotics:

Gaining more knowledge into the makeup and traits of the gut microbiota—a microbial ecosystem—is the aim of contemporary probiotic research. It is crucial to remember that each strain of probiotic has a different impact. Since bacterial strains can differ widely in their probiotic activity even within a species, every probiotic strain has a distinct health claim. Because of this, describing each probiotic's distinct qualities requires mentioning the strain. To achieve this, molecular methods like as pulsed-field gel electrophoresis for strain typing, 16S RNA sequencing, and DNA-DNA hybridization might be used to genetic identification. Rapid quantitative and qualitative insights into the gut microbiome's composition may be obtained by the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) approach. [8] Furthermore, a variety of probiotic pills are said to include several strains. The advantages of utilizing a single strain alone or in

combination might differ. Everybody has a different combination of gut bacteria that are involved in certain functions, such immunomodulation, gut mucosal barrier maintenance, and nutrition metabolism. Though the phrase "probiotics" may also apply to other types of bacteria, including Streptococcus, Enterococcus, Saccharomyces (a yeast strain), and Bacillus, it is most often linked with the common strains of Bifidobacterium and Lactobacillus. Numerous probiotic strains have been selected based on predetermined parameters. Certain bacteria that do not usually colonize the gastrointestinal tract, such Lactobacillus bulgaricus, streptococcus thermophilus, and Leonostoc species, may also be classified as probiotics. The gut's microbial balance is not significantly impacted by these bacteria's colonization or activity there. They do, nonetheless, profoundly impact the food sector. To find new strains and the future kind that may be probiotics, a lot of research is being done. Before being put into use, these new strains need to be assessed and scrutinized using established and verified selection standards. [12] [15]

2.3. Requisites for Selection of Safe and Effective Probiotics:

The scientific definition of probiotics and the criteria approving their appropriate use were developed eighteen years earlier. The goal of delivering live microorganisms is to help the therapeutic function take primacy. The majority of probiotics are marketed as foods or medications (tablets, powders, and other formulations) that include living microorganisms. There is a large range of dietary items that can accommodate probiotic strains, including yogurt, cheese, ice cream, buttermilk, powdered milk, and fermented milk. Given that probiotics are undoubtedly extremely sensitive to a variety of environmental stresses, including heat, oxygen, acidity, and other conditions, their viability and feasibility are essential considerations when creating probiotic-based foods. [13] [16] The market for probiotic food products is expanding globally as a result of the constant stream of studies that show their potential health advantages for consumers. Because commonly utilised bacteria are frequently isolated from clinical infection sites, probiotic safety and product compatibility with microorganisms are critical considerations. Their safety and

infectiousness have come under scrutiny as a result. Nevertheless, since their separation is the consequence of opportunistic infection—which might be brought on by cancer, skin injuries, chronic illnesses, or drug-induced abnormalities—it is doubtful that they require generalised infectivity. In actuality, Bifidobacterium and Lactobacillus seldom cause infections in people. This lack of virulence extends to immunocompromised individuals as well as all age groups. [11] It is not an easy undertaking to evaluate the safety of probiotics from many perspectives. For an in vitro investigation of multiple components, it is, nevertheless, rather simple. Numerous studies involving both humans and animals have been proposed to evaluate the safety standards of probiotics by examining the strain's intrinsic properties, its pharmacokinetics (i.e., survival, intestinal activity, faecal and mucosal recovery), and the interaction between the strain and host. However, there is disagreement about these parameters' values because operating practices are not standardised. Therefore, studies that are tailored to a target audience and their role should be the best course of action. While many probiotic strains are widely regarded as risk-free, safe, and seldom have adverse host effects reported, it is still necessary to consider the following considerations when evaluating a probiotic's safety and efficacy: [13] [18]

- Genetically identified at the strain, species, and genus levels (whole genome strain characterization)
- Not infectious or pathogenic.
- The gene for transferable antibiotic resistance shouldn't be present.
- Non-toxic [no hazardous materials such as amines, ammonia, indole, or phenol are formed]
- Capable of surviving in sufficient numbers throughout intestinal transit [tolerant of bile and acid] [111]
- Bile salt hydrolase activity [prevents carcinogenesis by deconjugating biliary salt].
- Antimicrobial action [ability to colonise, stick to the mucosal epithelium, and drive out pathogens through competitive exclusion]
- Capable of provoking pathogenic bacteria [the study conducted in vitro is dependent on the mass of microbial cells, the buffer component, the

duration of fermentation, and the growth medium] [9]

- Stable and able to survive in storage conditions [increases immunomodulation, increases gut adhesion, and decreases gut permeability]
- Clinically proven and verified health impacts [that require testing in a human randomised controlled study.
- Specified strain intended for usage with humans and animals.

Aside from that, there are a few more factors that need to be discussed in the safety analysis, including the activity of platelets aggregating and the activity of mucus degrading. Different strains of *L. Rhamnosus*, which have more activity than laboratory strains, were isolated by Harry et al. from infective endocarditis. This implies that they might have an infectious characteristic that aids in the development of endocarditis. The generation of the enzymes glycosidase and protease is responsible for mucous degradation activity. These enzymes have the potential to break down intestinal mucous glycoproteins, leading to infectious endocarditis. The effectiveness of this suggested mechanism was not discovered by Ruserler et al. in their investigation of lactobacillus and bifidobacterium. As a result, determining the infectivity associated with the glycoprotein and lectin-containing outer layer structure is crucial. [13] [15]

MECHANISM OF ACTION:

Uncertainty surrounds the methods by which probiotics produce their positive benefits. However, many of their positive effects may be linked to a number of hypothesized processes. One of these approaches is the competition between probiotics for cell attachments, or adhesion sites. Several pathogenic organisms must establish a link with the GI tract epithelium in order to invade the body. But some strains of bifidobacterial and lactobacilli may stick to epithelium, functioning as "colonization barriers" to prevent pathogens from adhering to mucosa. "To demonstrate this effect, *Lactobacillus plantarum* 299v and *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* strain GG were used." These two microorganisms exhibited *E. Coli*'s potential to stick to human colon cells. Another mode of action is the creation of antimicrobial chemicals, which may modify the

microbial flora. Numerous "lactobacilli" and "bifidobacteria" species create bacteriocins and other antibacterial substances. Bacteriocins may be characterized as "compounds produced by bacteria that have a biologically active protein moiety and a bactericidal action". Other physiologically active chemicals that lactic acid bacteria may generate include diacetyl, hydrogen peroxide, and short-chain fatty acids. The chemical is released secreted by probiotic bacteria, which alters the microbiota in a beneficial manner. [13] [16] Certain species of lactobacilli and bifidobacteria do not release chemicals with antimicrobial characteristics, while others do have very nonspecific actions that may be damaging to both pathogenic and benign bacteria. Probiotics have been demonstrated to enhance immunity as well. Increased natural killer cell counts, increased macrophage phagocytic activity, or

increased immunoglobulin-A (IgA) synthesis are some examples of how the immune system may respond. Increased IgA production may enhance the composition of the microflora by reducing the amount of harmful bacteria in the gut. Because of their immunomodulatory features, probiotics have been connected to possible therapy advantages for a variety of disorders, such as urogenital infections, food allergies, pouchitis, and inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), in addition to functioning as a vaccination booster. It is likely that probiotics will compete with pathogens for nutrients. This topic involves *Clostridium difficile*, a potentially hazardous bacteria that feeds on monosaccharides. Probiotics may eat most of the available monosaccharides when there are plenty of them, which inhibits *C. difficile* from developing.

Schematic diagram illustrating potential or known mechanisms whereby probiotic bacteria might impact on the microbiota. These mechanisms include (1) competition for dietary ingredients as growth substrates, (2) bioconversion of, for example, sugars into fermentation products with inhibitory properties, (3) production of growth substrates, for example, EPS or vitamins, for other bacteria, (4) direct antagonism by bacteriocins, (5) competitive exclusion for binding sites, (6) improved barrier function, (7) reduction of inflammation, thus altering intestinal properties for colonization and persistence within, and (8) stimulation of innate immune response (by unknown mechanisms). IEC: epithelial cells, DC: dendritic cells, T: T-cells. For further details, see main text.

4.2. Classification Of Probiotics :

Probiotics nowadays come in a wide variety of forms. The following discussion might be useful to gain a better understanding of the nomenclature and

classification used for bacteria. A bacterium's genus is its first name (e.g., *Lactobacillus*). It is a fairly broad term that describes a classification of species according to shared characteristics, like physical attributes, end products of metabolism, and metabolic requirements. A bacterium's second name

is species. It falls into a far more specific category, depending on similar traits that set them apart from other species. Even more precisely, strains separate members of the same species into smaller groups according to a number of characteristics that set them apart from other members of the species.

“Common probiotic microorganisms		
1	<i>Lactobacillus spp.</i>	acidophilus
		plantarum
		rhamnosus
		paracasei
		fermentum
		reuteri
		Johnsonii
		brevis
		casei
		lactis
		delbrueckii
2	<i>Bifidobacterium spp</i>	Breve animalis
		infantis
		longum
		bifidum
		thermophilum
		adolescentis
	<i>Bacillus spp.</i>	gasseri
3	<i>Bacillus spp.</i>	coagulans
4	<i>Streptococcus spp.</i>	thermophilus
5	<i>Enterococcus spp.</i>	faecium
6	<i>Saccharomyces spp</i>	Cerevisiae”

5.1. Sources :

Fermented foods are created by a range of living microbial cultures growing and metabolically active. Many of these foods are rich in live microbes that may be beneficial. Sourdough bread and LMC pickles are examples of fermented foods that are processed after fermentation and do not contain active cultures in a form that is meant for ingestion. Foods that are fermented but usually do not contain probiotic microorganisms include many types of cheese, pickles, kimchi (a Korean dish made from fermented cabbage), sauerkraut (fermented cabbage), miso (a fermented soybean-based paste), raw unfiltered apple cider vinegar made from fermented apple sugars, and kombucha (a fermented tea). [18] Probiotic bacteria can enter the human gut through cheese. Research indicates that non-fermented foods also contain probiotic bacteria. For instance, in vitro research has demonstrated that certain bacterial strains isolated

from fruits (*Lactobacillus plantarum*, *L. paracasei*, and *Staphylococcus carnosus*) and meat (*L. sakei*, *L. curvatus*) can display functional and metabolic characteristics similar to those of gut bacteria in humans. [18][5] Another place to get probiotics is in the human intestine. This source has identified many of the probiotic strains that are utilised today, such as *L. gasseri* and *L. reuteri*. Furthermore, it has been reported that *L. fermentum*, which was isolated from biopsy samples of human colonic mucosa, demonstrates ABP. Bacteria develop an adaptation response to mild stress circumstances such nutrient-rich or nutrient-poor media, pH, and salt content. Through the control of protein complexes, signal transmission, or gene expression, food properties might even be changed. [14] [15]

5.2. Food Application of Probiotics:

Foods with health advantages beyond proper nutrition are currently being developed as a result of growing knowledge of functional foods. Over the past 20 years, there has been a rise in consumer interest in functional foods, particularly those that include probiotics. Certain health advantages of probiotics have been linked to their presence in commercial food products. This has caused industry to concentrate on various ways to incorporate probiotics into food items and to develop a new range of "probiotic health" foods. This section will provide an overview of the typical uses of probiotics in food items. [2]

.2.1. Dairy Based Probiotics:

Because of its natural qualities and the fact that most milk and milk products are kept at a chilled temperature, milk and its products provide suitable vehicles for probiotic bacteria. Many commercial dairy products, such as fresh and sour milk, yoghurt, cheese, etc., include probiotics. Dairy products are crucial in the delivery of probiotic bacteria to humans because they offer probiotic bacteria an environment that is conducive to their growth and survival. Applying probiotics to dairy products requires consideration of a number of parameters, including the survivability of probiotics in dairy, the end products' physical, chemical, and organoleptic qualities, the impact of probiotics on health, and regulatory and labelling difficulties. [53]

5.2.1.1. Drinkable Fresh Milk and Fermented Milk:

Dairy drinks were the first commercially available probiotic-carrying food product and are currently consumed in greater amounts than other probiotic beverages. Fortified dairy beverages (including probiotics, prebiotics, fibres, polyphenols, peptides, sterol, stanols, minerals, vitamins, and fish oil) and whey-based beverages are the two categories into which functional dairy beverages fall. *L. rhamnosus* GG is the probiotic bacteria that is most frequently utilised in the production of dairy products. The bile resistance and *L. rhamnosus* GG acid make this probiotic ideal for industrial use. Avnikirmaci and Özer found that the most often used probiotics are *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, and *Lactobacillus plantarum*, as evidenced by a number of examples of

commercial probiotic dairy beverages. It has been documented that a number of variables influence the probiotic cultures' ability to survive in fermented milks. The viability of probiotic bacteria is impacted by a number of factors, including pH, dissolved oxygen content, redox potential, hydrogen peroxide, starter microbes, potential flavouring compound presence, and various additives (including preservatives), all of which have been linked to the production and storage of fermented milks [1, 4, 5]. Consumers can now purchase a variety of dairy products that are infused with probiotic bacteria, such as Actimel, Gaio, ProViva, Nu-Trish A-B, Bifidus milk, *Acidophilus* buttermilk, Yakult, Procult drink, Sweet *Acidophilus* milk, and *Acidophilus* milk. Due to their limited proteolytic activity and incapacity to use lactose, probiotics like *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* strains grow poorly in milk. Additionally, these bacteria require certain chemicals for development, which are absent from milk. Many chemicals have been explored in milk to enhance the viability and growth of probiotics in dairy products. It has been discovered that the presence of citrus fibre in fermented milks increases probiotic bacterial growth and survival [6]. Certain beneficial benefits of adding soygerm powder have been shown when fermented milk is produced using *Lactobacillus reuteri*. During fermentation, soygerm powder may release significant bioactive isoflavones that may shield *L. reuteri* from the toxicity of bile salts in the small intestine. Additional compounds were reported to exist, including tryptone, fructooligosaccharides (FOS), aseinomaclopeptides (CMP), whey protein concentrate (WPC), yeast extracts, certain amino acids, nucleotide precursors, and an iron source. Furthermore, the vitality of probiotic bacteria in fermented milk is highly dependent on the choice of probiotic strains and optimization of manufacturing parameters (both formulation qualities and storage conditions). [19]

5.2.1.2. Yogurt:

One of the first sources of probiotics was yoghurt, which is still a well-liked probiotic product today. Yoghurt is well-known for its health advantages and nutritious content. [1] *L. delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus salivarius* subsp. *thermophilus* are the bacteria used in the production of yoghurt. Furthermore, additional lactobacilli and

bifidobacteria are occasionally introduced either during or following the yogurt-culturing process. These bacterial strains that make up the yoghurt culture are still thought to have some probiotic qualities. It is important to take into account the probiotics' viability and their proteolytic activity in yoghurt. The survival of *Bifidobacterium* spp. and *Lactobacillus* in yoghurt can be impacted by a variety of variables. Probiotic bacterial strains, pH, the amount of dissolved oxygen and hydrogen peroxide, the concentration of metabolites like lactic and acetic acids, the media's ability to act as a buffer, and the storage temperature are a few of these. Despite being a popular probiotic delivery system, the majority of commercial yoghurt products have low viable cell counts when consumed. Probiotics' viability in yoghurt is dependent on the nutrients that are available, the growth stimulants and inhibitors that are present, the solute concentration, the inoculation level, the incubation temperature, the fermentation time, and temperature of storage. It was discovered that probiotic viability and survival in yoghurt varied depending on the strain. The primary causes of probiotic organisms losing their viability have been identified as the medium's decreasing pH and the buildup of organic acids as a consequence of growth and fermentation. The final pH attained during yoghurt fermentation seems to be the most significant factor influencing the viability and development of probiotics among the other parameters. Probiotics' ability to survive in the cell may also be impacted by the byproducts of organic acid metabolism during storage [16]. Given that berries and fruit may have antibacterial properties, adding fruit to yoghurt may negatively impact the viability of probiotics. An extremely high probiotic inoculation level in an effort to offset any possible viability loss could lead to a lower-than-expected product quality. It was discovered that the presence of probiotics affected the acidity, texture, flavour, and appearance of yoghurt [9]. However, probiotics in yoghurt may be more viable and stable if they are encapsulated in simple alginate beads, chitosan-coated alginate, alginate-starch, alginate-prebiotic, alginate-pectin, or in a whey protein-based matrix. Probiotics may also be added to yoghurt by adding prebiotics or cysteine. [13] [17]

2.1.3 Cheese:

Among dairy products, yoghurt and milk are the most popular sources of probiotics. Other carriers, like cheese, appear to be a good fit, though. In comparison to yoghurt and fermented milks, cheeses have a variety of benefits, including a better pH and buffering capacity, greater nutritional value, high energy, a more solid consistency, a substantially larger fat content, and a longer shelf life [8, 11]. Numerous studies have shown that probiotics in cheese have a high viable cell count and a high survival rate near the end of their shelf life [15, 18, 12, 13]. Cheese's probiotics have been shown to greatly boost the amount of probiotic cells in the gut and to survive transit through a simulated human gastrointestinal tract [12]. Comparing the serving sizes of cheese and yoghurt, it is evident that cheese requires a higher viability and density of probiotic cells in order to offer the same health advantages. When Danisco chose to examine the development and survival of probiotic strains in cheese in 2006, cheese was first introduced to the probiotic sector [14]. There weren't many probiotic cheese products available on the market at the time. Less than 10% of the germs were found in the cheese whey, according to the test. The Mills DA in Oslo, Norway was the first to manufacture a commercial probiotic cheese based on this method. These days, the market is filled with more than 200 different types of probiotic-containing commercial cheeses, including fresh, semi-hard, and hard varieties. As a probiotic carrier, semi-hard and hard cheese require a comparatively high inoculation dose of bacteria (about 4 to 5 times) and a relatively low daily intake when compared to yoghurt. Cottage cheese, being fresh, has a limited shelf life and should be stored at a chilled temperature. A high daily consumption is advised. Therefore, it might be considered a meal that has a great deal of potential for use as a probiotic carrier. [4]

5.2.2. Non-Dairy Based Probiotic Product:

Since dairy products give probiotic bacteria a favourable environment that promotes their growth and survival, they are the primary sources of probiotic bacteria in human diets. Nonetheless, there is a market for vegetarian probiotic products due to the rise in vegetarianism among consumers in affluent nations. Vegetarians and consumers with lactose sensitivity have demonstrated a strong interest in nondairy probiotic products. Approximately 75% of people

worldwide are lactose intolerant, according to the National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases (NIDDK) of the United States National Institutes of Health. It is extremely difficult to design novel nondairy probiotic food products that satisfy customer expectations for health benefits [19, 9]. Granato and associates provide an overview of the development of functional foods, focusing on nondairy meals that have probiotic bacterial strains [12].

2.2.1. Vegetable Based Probiotic Product:

Vegetable fermentation has been understood since antiquity. One viable medium for probiotic delivery is fermented vegetables. It does, however, demonstrate that the low fermentation temperature of vegetables poses a challenge to the entry of the conventional probiotic bacteria, *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Bifidobacterium*. When fermenting, probiotics like *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, and *Lactobacillus plantarum* are more suited to the vegetable [14]. Nevertheless, probiotic bacteria grow quite quickly in plant-based substrates when the temperature is adjusted to 37°C. [2]

2.2.2 Fruit Based Probiotic Product:

These days, there is a growing interest in the creation of probiotic products based on fruit juice. Fruit juices are rich in healthy elements, making them a perfect vehicle for probiotics [16, 17]. Fruit juices are seen to be pleasant and healthful, and their flavour characteristics appeal to people of all ages. The fruits are high in antioxidants, dietary fibres, minerals, vitamins, and dairy-free ingredients that may make them unsuitable for consumption by some demographic groups. These qualities enable the selection of suitable probiotic strains to produce tasty, healthful fruit juice. Probiotic cultures would, however, [18] [12] have different taste profiles from typical, nonfunctional items in terms of their sensory impact. Consumers do not like the distinct flavours and aromas that have been observed when *L. plantarum* is added to orange juices. However, if information about their health advantages is given, people will prefer them over regular orange juice. Various approaches have been taken to lessen the perception of offensive flavours and scents in probiotic fruit juice. Lucknow and colleagues found

that adding 10% (v/v) of tropical fruit juices—mostly pineapple, but also mango or passion fruit—could cover the noticeable off-flavors from probiotics that frequently lead to customer dissatisfaction. [20]

CONCLUSION:

Well-conducted clinical trials have shown the beneficial effects of probiotics on health in a range of clinical situations. It is clear that there is a critical need for these probiotic-based methods with the advent of the functional food concept. The word "synbiotics" was very recently developed to refer to nutritional supplements and foods that improve health that are used as functional food elements in human diets. To demonstrate the safety, efficacy, and limitations of a potential probiotic, evaluate its impact on the immune system in both healthy and sick individuals, examine the consequences of long-term use, and ascertain whether it is better than currently available treatments, more rigorous and validated clinical trials are required. This is true even when more encouraging potential side effects of probiotics are being noted by further study. Furthermore, the potential for genetically modified probiotics to be used in the treatment of clinical issues calls for the creation of a stringent safety protocol to prevent the release of the genetic alteration into the environment.

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